

Isolation and Characterization of Novel Actinomycetes from Soil for the Production of Antimicrobial

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Article Information	Abstract
<p>Article history: Received: 10-02-18 Revised: 20.02.2018 Accepted: 25.02.2018</p>	<p><i>In the present study, 25 isolates were isolated from the local soil samples and characterized as Actinomycetes, out of which one isolate (No.3) was found to be potent producer of antimicrobial substance that inhibited all the test organisms including gram positive bacteria, gram negative bacteria, yeast and fungi hence exposing its broad spectrum activity</i></p>
<p>Keywords: Actinomycetes. Antimicrobial substance.</p>	

Introduction-

The quest for new and novel antibiotics had been always a keen interest for scientists. A number of antibiotics have been discovered to fulfill the needs. But with the continuation of antibiotics, the resistance to the drug is proliferating. Bacteria that have become resistance to one antibiotic also found to build resistance to others [1]. The strike back of pathogens has revitalized the search of new drugs. Novel antibiotics are required to counter various microorganisms. It is estimated that only 10% of the estimated total number of microbial species are known [2]. These microorganisms seem to be virtually an unlimited source of novel structure with variety of potential applications.

Actinomycetes are a diverse group of hydrophilic prokaryotes forming hyphae at some stage of their growth. Actinomycetes are very important for medical point of view being the producer of most of the antibiotics [3]. Nearly 11,900 antibiotics had been described by 1994 and estimated that about 50% are produced by *Streptomyces spp.* Also, Actinomycetes are the largest producer of secondary metabolites that help in maintaining defense mechanism, inhibiting other competing cells, functioning as germicide and showing anti bacterial, anti fungal or anti tumor activity.[4][5][6][7].

In view of the immense potential of Actinomycetes for novel antimicrobial drug, the present study was designed, in which we

planned to isolate the Antibiotic producing Actinomycetes, their characterization, Assessment of microbial activity followed by evolution of antimicrobial activity of selected Actinomycetes against some resistant clinical isolates. Actinomycetes had always been a good source and the present study is an added example to this series.

Materials and Methods-

The different soil samples were collected from various sites of Noida. Soil samples were mixed with distilled water and then heated for 1 hour at 50-55°C. 1 gm of soil was added to 100 ml of sterilized normal saline and stirred vigorously for 10 minutes. Then the upper layer is taken and diluted by normal saline followed by serial dilution. Further the suspension was inoculated by pour plate method following strict aseptic conditions on the selective media. Pure colonies were maintained on the agar plate by quadrate streaking and also on slants as well as in glycerol stock at -20 °C for further examination.

A large scale screening was conducted in order to identify Actinomycetes from the native soil samples. In order to identify, staining experiments and Biochemical tests were conducted. (Graph No.1 and 2). Then screening was done to access antimicrobial activity. It was done by two methods qualitatively and quantitatively. In Qualitative screening the test culture was inoculated on agar along with the microorganisms to test the antagonistic behaviour of the test culture to the microorganisms. In Quantitative screening, Agar well assay was used to determine the susceptibility or resistance of a microbial strain.

All the experiments were carried out at Zoology department, Government Post Graduate College, Noida during 2008-2009.

Conclusion –

In the present study, 20 soil samples were collected, Out of which, 25 isolates of Actinomycetes were isolated which were different in their colony morphology. The isolates then subjected to identification which was carried out by their morphological and staining behavior. The isolates showed the characteristic feature of Actinomycetes such as filamentous form, being gram positive and non motile nature. The strains were then identified by their biochemical characteristics. All of the isolates were catalase positive and oxidase negative. They had not liquefied gelatin, showed aesculin hydrolysis, hydrogen sulphide production and urea hydrolysis. All of the isolates had not showed melanin synthesis on peptone yeast iron agar.

These isolates were then subjected to antimicrobial testing. The isolates showed different antimicrobial and antifungal activity. Out of 25 isolated 20 (80%) showed antimicrobial activity. Four (16%) isolates showed activity against *E. coli* and 6 (24%) isolates were found to be effective against *Bacillus subtilis* and one (4%) isolates were effective against both gram positive and gram negative bacteria. Out of 25 isolates 20 (80%) showed antifungal activity. 6 (24%) against *Candida albicans*, 19 (76%) against *Aspergillus niger*, 2 (8%) against both yeast and fungi and 1 (4%) against all microorganisms tested.

The isolates of qualitative screening were subjected to quantitative screening. It showed that the strain possesses maximum

activity against gram positive and gram negative bacteria. So it can be suggested that the antibiotic screened had a broad spectrum activity.

Future scope-These strains can be further tested for proper identification up to species level, using cell wall chemo type, whole cell sugar pattern, peptidoglycan type, phospholipids type and G+C content of DNA resulting in complete characterization and proper identification of antimicrobial substance.

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Graph 1: Morphological and staining characteristics, where ■ shows filamentous colony shape and positive test in case of gram staining and motility testing.

No. of Isolates
 Graph 2: Biochemical tests of isolates, where ■ shows positive test

Graph 3: Qualitative screening of isolates, where ■ shows + activity, ■ shows ++ activity, ■ shows +++ activity and shows - activity.

Graph 4: Quantitative screening of isolates, where ■ shows + activity, ■ shows ++ activity, ■ shows +++ activity and shows - activity.